

Crisis Navigator for Rapid Mobilisation of Science Communication

For Journalists

Underlying
Conflicts

Framing and
Sensemaking

Power

Trust

Values and
Emotion

Ethical
issues

Reflective
practice

Collaboration

Pre-Crisis

Imminent Crisis

Actual Crisis

Post-Crisis

Introduction

The **Crisis Navigator** is designed as a **strategic resource for diverse science communication stakeholders who communicate science in times of crises**. Rather than offering standardized guidelines (“what to do”), the Crisis Navigator functions as a **sensitising tool** – a conceptual and practical aid that helps communicators *notice, reflect on, and interpret* subtle aspects of their work. Here, the guiding question is: **How can journalists communicate about science when a crisis emerges?**

The present tool is targeted towards **non-science (generalist) journalists** working across all forms of media; whether in print, radio or social media. Non-science journalists are media professionals who cover a wide range of topics, rather than specializing in science, and who may be assigned to report on science-related issues during a crisis, such as a pandemic, environmental disaster, or technological accident. **Acting as intermediaries between complex events and the broader public, their reporting can significantly influence public understanding, trust, and the potential for constructive outcomes during and after the crisis.**

The Crisis Navigator is structured along four stages: *pre-, imminent, actual, and post-crisis*, taking into account the **evolving dynamics of a crisis**. Ultimately, this Crisis Navigator serves as a guide for journalists to better imagine and anticipate what they are – and could be – up against when communicating science in times of crisis, supporting them to navigate their practice in a more informed and reflective manner.

Challenge: Complexity and uncertainty

GUIDING QUESTION

What are good ways to convey the current state of knowledge and uncertainty to broader publics?

To answer the guiding question, consider:

Newsworthiness: Sudden crises, like emergencies, and long-term crises differ in perceived newsworthiness. Media often prioritize immediate, dramatic events. In emergencies, journalists must balance urgency and accuracy. Long-term crises, however, require broader coverage that not only addresses immediate risks but also highlights long-term impacts, recovery, and systemic lessons, which are often underreported.

Information gaps: Journalists should identify and monitor what information is available to whom, where and when; and be alert to any gaps that exist or may emerge in understanding the situation before, during, and after reporting. They must avoid overstating conclusions, exaggerating risks, or implying false certainty, which can spread misinformation and undermine public trust. At the same time, “good enough” information – reliable and actionable – is often sufficient, as clarity and timeliness can be more important than completeness during crises.

Science and evidence: How complex is the science, and what evidence supports it? Journalists should aim to integrate multiple perspectives in response to these questions to offer a balanced and comprehensive understanding of an issue, while acknowledging limitations and areas of ongoing research or debate. By verifying information, providing context, and communicating findings accurately, they help the public make informed decisions. They must also balance accuracy with timeliness, delivering actionable information while clarifying what is known, unknown, or evolving.

Voice: Journalists should consider who is seen as credible and which voices deserve public attention, weighing the impact of giving visibility to certain stakeholders or knowledge. It is also important to avoid false balance between scientific consensus and unsupported claims. Rigid “both-sides” framing can distort public understanding by amplifying marginal views, such as vaccine misinformation. Instead, journalists should practice evidentiary balance, giving weight to perspectives based on the strength of their scientific evidence.

Underlying conflicts

GUIDING QUESTION

What does each stakeholder need?

Underlying conflicts can stem from differences in values or interests among individuals or groups. They can exert a significant influence on attitudes, behaviors, and interactions. Identifying and understanding these underlying tensions before a crisis emerges is crucial, as it enables journalists to anticipate potential boiling points and provide more balanced, contextualized reporting when a crisis does unfold. By adopting inclusive and transparent approaches to reporting that do not shy away from the question “What is at stake for whom and why?”, journalists can help to shed light on underlying conflicts and contribute to more effective and durable solutions to urgent societal issues.

Collaboration

GUIDING QUESTION

How can journalists facilitate constructive exchanges between concerned stakeholders?

Collaboration is vital in science journalism to foster constructed exchanges between stakeholders and ensure accurate, coordinated reporting. Working closely with trusted experts strengthens fact-checking, credibility, and access to diverse perspectives. Science journalists play a key role by maintaining trusted expert networks across fields. Before a crisis occurs, journalists should: (1) understand their audiences’ values and emotions, (2) build relationships with experts and local sources, (3) prepare clear communication strategies, and (4) test tools and platforms to enable timely, transparent, and inclusive communication.

Framing and sensemaking

GUIDING QUESTION

How do different stakeholders frame and make sense of scientific information and science reporting?

While framing refers to how information is presented, sensemaking concerns how individuals make sense of the information they receive. Through framing, journalists emphasize certain aspects of a topic while downplaying others. It is therefore essential to use terms such as “urgent,” “crisis,” and “issue” carefully, as while they convey severity, they can also obscure underlying causes and provoke apathy or fear. Journalists should reflect on their own and others’ framing, avoiding alarmism and aiming to empower audiences through a sense of agency and action. While framing shapes how scientific information is understood, journalists cannot control audience sensemaking practices. Science reporting can support sensemaking during crises by clearly explaining uncertainties and contradictions, connecting to diverse personal and social contexts, and adapting messages to cultural sensitivities.

Ethical issues

GUIDING QUESTION

How can journalism be supportive of an ethically-sound and responsible crisis response?

Science journalism can facilitate responsibility, prevent misinformation, and support collaborative responses to the challenges at hand. It allows stakeholders to assess the performance of authorities and organizations and hold them accountable for their actions. It can also promote ethical public engagement by fostering trust through transparency, enabling inclusive reporting, empowering individuals with education, highlighting ethical considerations, addressing societal challenges, building partnerships, and embracing the diversity of cultural values and beliefs. An important consideration is that crises often involve ethical dilemmas, such as situations where full transparency may not be appropriate because it could endanger public safety or compromise investigations.

Values and emotions

GUIDING QUESTION

What is the role of values and emotions in journalism – and how can journalists engage with values and emotions productively?

Values and emotions are key to exploring and communicating the complexity of crises and urgent societal problems. Journalists are uniquely positioned to interpret public emotions and shape the tone of crisis communication. The emotions expressed by stakeholders can reveal the values at stake and help frame reporting that captures the human dimension of a crisis. People rarely evaluate scientific information on evidence alone; they also respond to the emotional cues and relational signals communicators convey, such as empathy, honesty, and openness. By connecting with values and emotions through interaction with general publics and civil society, trust and collaboration can also be upheld during crises.

Power

GUIDING QUESTION

Who has the ability to influence, shape, and control framing of reports and sensemaking of stakeholders and publics?

In science journalism, ‘power’ refers to the ability to influence, shape, or control how the scientific information is framed and how different stakeholders make sense of it. These processes involve various actors – including scientists, science communicators, policy-makers, media professionals, and the public – each holding varying degrees of influence and authority. Questions to consider are: What counts as valid knowledge? Who decides? Whose framing prevails? Understanding and navigating these power dynamics is essential for ethical and effective reporting that fosters informed decision-making, equity, and public trust.

Reflective practice

GUIDING QUESTION

How can journalists continuously learn from, and adapt to, crisis situations?

After a crisis peaks, continued coverage is crucial, as long-term impacts can be as significant as the event itself. Regular reflection on science reporting across all crisis stages is equally important. Journalists should engage in reflective practice, examining how their reporting is shaped by assumptions, emotions, and worldviews, and recognizing their own positions. Sustained coverage and reflection promote accountability, keep the public informed and engaged, and provide insights to improve responses in future crises.

Trust

GUIDING QUESTION

How can journalists enable, preserve, and build trust in times of crisis?

Although trust matters in all crisis phases, it is difficult to build during an imminent or active crisis, making the pre- and post-crisis phases especially important. Trust in scientific information is influenced not only on facts but also by relational, social, and emotional factors. Inclusive reporting that reflects diverse perspectives and values can strengthen connections with a wide variety of publics and foster credibility. Trust can be further nurtured by acknowledging emotions and the personal impacts of a crisis, and connecting with individual stories. Relational trust develops over time through consistent, reliable, accountable, and transparent interactions. Clear communication about how information is gathered and verified helps audiences recognize trustworthy sources. In contrast, sensationalism or clickbait can provoke alarm or denial, undermining effective crisis management.

Deliverable 2.1 Science Communication Rapid Mobilisation Roadmap

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